

Secondary Amenorrhea due to Primary Ovarian Insufficiency Following COVID-19 Vaccine: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Secondary amenorrhea is defined as the absence of menses for 3 months in a woman with previously regular cycles, or 6 months in a woman with previously irregular cycles. It's mainly due to genetic abnormalities, autoimmune damage, iatrogenic factors, viral infections, and toxins affecting ovary, hypothalamus, pituitary, and uterus. Ovarian etiologies account for 10% of cases. The global prevalence of primary ovarian insufficiency is 3.7%. Some case reports have linked primary ovarian insufficiency with immunizations and the development of anti-ovarian antibodies.

Case Report: A 38-year-old female presented with secondary amenorrhea for 2 years following the administration of mRNA COVID-19 vaccine. She had a history of endometriosis and multiple fibroids, which were previously managed with oral combined contraceptive pills and two laparotomy surgeries. After discontinuing her medications, she experienced recurrent hospitalizations because of heavy uterine bleeding, which was eventually treated with bilateral uterine arterial embolization. Her menstrual bleeding became very light after receiving the first vaccine dose, and completely stopped after the second dose. The patient had no significant physical findings except for being overweight. A gynecological evaluation confirmed primary ovarian insufficiency, and further investigations ruled out other potential causes of secondary amenorrhea.

Conclusion: The safety and benefits of the COVID-19 vaccines are crucial considerations when deciding whether to administer them. Risk assessment should be conducted and discussed with each patient, which may be challenging, particularly for individuals who are at a higher risk of getting vaccine-related complications.

Keywords: Primary ovarian insufficiency; Coronavirus disease; COVID-19 Vaccine

INTRODUCTION

Secondary amenorrhea is commonly encountered by women's healthcare providers. It is generally defined as the absence of menses for 3 months in a woman with previously regular monthly cycles, or the absence of menses for 6 months in a woman with previously irregular cycles.^[1] While the presentation is often similar, several potential

etiologies exist. Based on a series of 262 patients with amenorrhea of adult onset, the most common causes reported were as follows: ovary (40%), hypothalamus (35%), pituitary (17%), uterus (7%), and others (1%).^[2] Among the ovarian etiologies of secondary amenorrhea, primary ovarian insufficiency (POI) represented 10%.^[2] The global prevalence of POI is considerable, reaching 3.7%.^[3] This highlights the need to understand and detect the etiologies and risk factors earlier to improve women's health. Unfortunately, the underlying cause remains unidentified in the majority of cases. Known causes include genetic aberrations, autoimmune ovarian damage, iatrogenic factors (following surgical, radiotherapeutic, or chemotherapeutic interventions), and environmental factors such as viral infections and toxins.^[4] Among these causes, the presence or suspicion of an autoimmune disorder should be considered when encountering young women with a loss of menstrual regularity, especially when there is concomitant dysfunction in the immune system, as in patients known to have autoimmune diseases. There have been case reports linking POI with immunizations via anti-ovarian antibody formation.^[5] In our case, we are presenting a 38-year-old female with a previous history of regular menstrual cycles who experienced a complete cessation of menstrual bleeding following administration of the *coronavirus* disease 2019 (*COVID-19*) vaccine, which is unusual and unexpected after such an intervention. Many systematic reviews have been conducted to track menstrual irregularities after *COVID-19* vaccines administration to dispel concerns about the long-term likelihood of pregnancy delay, and amenorrhea has been reported in most of them.^[6]

CASE REPORT

A 38-year-old single female presented to our primary care clinic in February 2023 complaining of dysuria for the past few days due to cystitis, and absent menses for the last 2 years after receiving mRNA *COVID-19* vaccine.

The patient's menstrual history showed menarche at the age of 11 years, with regular and normal periods until the age of 16 when she started experiencing increased menstrual bleeding without a change in the length of her period. She also reported severe abdominal cramps during her period, indicating dysmenorrhea. Her medical record was insignificant, except for endometriosis and multiple fibroids, which were investigated and treated with oral combined contraceptive pills and two laparotomy surgeries in 2006 and 2011. She was doing well until she completely stopped taking the medications for multiple personal reasons, resulting in recurrent hospitalizations and emergency visits for heavy uterine bleeding. Eventually, she underwent bilateral uterine arterial embolization (UAE) in March 2020, which led to a marked improvement in her menstrual pain and bleeding for almost a year. However, after receiving her first *COVID-19* vaccine dose in March 2021, her menstrual bleeding became very light and lasted for less than 2 days. Following the administration of her second dose in April 2021, her periods stopped completely. She denied symptoms of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) infection, and her tests were negative before the onset of amenorrhea.

When inquired about postmenopausal symptoms, she reported recent complaints of hot flashes, fatigue, and a decrease in the amount of vaginal discharge. Considering the differential diagnoses for the patient's secondary amenorrhea, she reported no excessive physical training or significant fluctuations in body weight in recent years. Her psychological state was carefully evaluated, ruling out any psychosocial stress. She denied having acne, hirsutism, or virilization symptoms. The patient also denied experiencing any thyroid-related symptoms such as palpitations, nervousness, tremors, changes in bowel habits, or temperature intolerance. She did not complain of polyuria, polydipsia, insomnia, headache, visual disturbances, galactorrhea, or breast enlargement. She denied

chronic use of medications or exposure to radiotherapy or chemotherapy. Her family history was unremarkable for POI or other related diseases. The patient expressed her disinterest in vaccination, stating that she only took the *COVID-19* vaccine as it was required for travel. She has no known allergies, and her surgical records are insignificant except for what was previously mentioned. The patient has never smoked, consumed alcohol, or used illicit drugs. She regularly exercises by brisk walking and does not follow any dietary restrictions.

During our evaluation, her temperature was 36.7°C, pulse was 85 beats per minute, and blood pressure was 97/67 mmHg. She weighed 71 kg, had a height of 1.62 m, and a body mass index of 27 kg/m². The systemic physical examination of cardiovascular, pulmonary, abdominal, neurological, musculoskeletal, and external genitalia was unremarkable. We did not observe any signs of hirsutism, acne, striae, acanthosis nigricans, or depigmented lesions. There were no galactorrhea or abnormalities upon breast examination.

We conducted several blood tests for celiac disease, thyroid disease, adrenal deficit, connective tissue disease (CTD), diabetes mellitus, and hyperprolactinemia. Postmenopausal levels of luteinizing hormone (LH), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), and estradiol were confirmed, accompanied by low anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) and testosterone. The gynecological evaluation and the biochemical results suggested POI (Table 1).

Table 1: Blood tests values and reference range (case report section)

Blood test	Patient's result	Reference range
<i>Hemoglobin</i>	11.9 gm/dL	12.0 - 15.0 gm/dL
Mean corpuscular volume	91.5 fL	83.0 - 101.0 fL
Red cell distribution width	13.1%	11.6 - 14.5%
Ferritin	132 mcg/L	11 - 304 mcg/L
Urea	3.4 mmol/L	2.1 - 8.1 mmol/L
Creatinine	48 umol/L	38 - 97 umol/L
Glomerular filtration rate	>90 mL/min/1.73m ²	>90 mL/min/1.73m ²
Sodium	142 mmol/L	135 - 145 mmol/L
Potassium	3.6 mmol/L	3.6 - 5.1 mmol/L
Calcium	2.44 mmol/L	2.1 - 2.6 mmol/L
Chloride	105.9 mmol/L	96.0 - 110.0 mmol/L
Total Protein	71 gm/L	66 - 87 gm/L
Albumin	44 gm/L	35 - 50 gm/L
Alkaline phosphatase	48.7 U/L	33.5 - 129.0 U/L
Alanine transaminase	37.0 U/L	0.0 - 30.0 U/L
Aspartate transferase	31 U/L	0 - 31 U/L
Hemoglobin A1C	5.4%	<5.7%
Beta-human chorionic gonadotrophin	<1 mIU/mL	0-5 mIU/mL
17-hydroxyprogesterone	1.453 nmol/L	Follicular phase: 0.3 - 2.4 nmol/L Luteal phase: 1.8 - 6.9 nmol/L Ovulation: 0.9 - 4.2 nmol/L Postmenopausal: 0.4 - 1.6 nmol/L
AMH	<0.07 pmol/L	30-34 years: 4.1 -58.0 pmol/L 35-39 years: 1.1 -53.5 pmol/L 40-44 years: 0.19 -39.1 pmol/L 45-50 years: 0.07 - 19.3 pmol/L PCOS: 13.3 - 135 pmol/L
Estradiol	<18.4 pmol/L	Follicular phase: 45.4 - 854 pmol/L Midcycle phase: 151 - 1461 pmol/L Luteal phase: 81.9 - 1251 pmol/L Postmenopausal: <18.4 - 505 pmol/L
FSH	79.1 IU/L	Follicular phase: 4 - 13 IU/L

		Ovulation phase: 5 - 22 IU/L Luteal phase: 2 - 8 IU/L Postmenopausal: 26 - 135 IU/L
LH	29 IU/L	Follicular phase: 2 - 13 IU/L Ovulation phase: 14 - 96 IU/L Luteal phase: 1 - 11 IU/L Postmenopausal: 8 - 59 IU/L
Testosterone	<0.09 nmol/L	0.29 - 1.67 nmol/L
Prolactin	161 mIU/L	102 - 495 mIU/L
Thyroid stimulating hormone	0.99 mIU/L	0.30 - 4.20 mIU/L
Free T4	15.5 pmol/L	11.0 - 23.3 pmol/L
Anti-transglutaminase IgA Ab	Negative	Negative
Anti-transglutaminase IgG Ab	Negative	Negative
Antinuclear antibody CTD	Negative	Negative

DISCUSSION

COVID-19 vaccines have different mechanisms of action; however, they all share the goal of inducing a humoral antibody response against viral particles.^[7] There have been reported cases of secondary amenorrhea due to POI following the human papillomavirus vaccine.^[8] A retrospective study based on a survey included women aged 18-41 years who had normal menstrual cycles before receiving the *COVID-19* vaccine. After the vaccine, the following changes were reported: cycle frequency (normal 43.47%, infrequent 25%, and frequent 31.53%), cycle regularity (regular 51.08%, irregular 42.93%, and absent/amenorrhea 5.97%), cycle duration (normal 65.21%, prolonged 26.08%, absent/amenorrhea 8.69%), and cycle volume (heavy 41.84%, light 20.65%, and absent/amenorrhea 6.52%). The study concluded that *COVID-19* vaccination can influence the menstrual cycle and cause alterations.^[9] Another study showed that there was no statistically significant difference between pre-vaccine and post-vaccine (60-90 days after vaccination) AMH values, which reflects ovarian reserve.^[10] However, primary infertility due to the development of anti-ovarian antibodies after SARS-CoV-2 infection has been reported.^[11]

Our patient had a history of heavy uterine bleeding managed eventually by bilateral UAE in March 2020. The onset of amenorrhea caused by ovarian failure after UAE has been reported, possibly due to the occlusion of ovarian arterial supply via uterine arterial communications. However, POI after UAE remains very infrequent. Data from randomized trials and case series suggest that ovarian function degradation may occur after UAE, but mainly in women older than 45 years, with little evidence of an impact on women younger than 40 years of age, which is the case with our patient.^[12]

CONCLUSION

The safety and benefits of the *COVID-19* vaccines are crucial considerations when deciding whether to administer them. Risk assessment should be conducted and discussed with each patient, which may be challenging, particularly for individuals who are at a higher risk of getting vaccine-related complications.

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Data availability: The data supporting the findings of this case report are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Abbreviations:

Primary ovarian insufficiency (POI)

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19)

Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)

Uterine arterial embolization (UAE)

Luteinizing hormone (LH)

Follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH)

Anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH)

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